

CHEMICAL SCIENCES

INFLUENCE OF SURFACE TREATMENT OF HEMP INSULATION MATERIAL ON FIBER MORPHOLOGY AND WATER ABSORPTION

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Abstract

Hemp is one of the promising resources for application in the modern building sector. Hemp insulation materials have a number of distinctive properties, they are comfortable and easy to use during installation. The main advantages of hemp insulation are high acoustic properties, reusability, ease and simplicity of installation, low levels of toxins and hazardous emissions, reliability and durability in handling, transport and construction on site. However, compared to synthetic polymer materials, hemp insulation materials have high cost and the need for thicker walls due to lower thermal conductivity. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was used to study the surface morphology of insulating hemp material treated with a fire-retardant composition based on liquid glass, sodium hydroorthophosphate, and thiourea. Using energy dispersive (EDS) microanalysis, the elemental composition of the material was identified. The water absorption of the samples was studied.

Keywords: microroughness, water absorption, aqueous solution of sodium hydrogen orthophosphate, liquid glass, thiourea, impregnating composition, scanning electron microscopy, elemental analysis

Nowadays insulation of houses and non-residential premises is global challenge. Good thermal insulation requires a material that not only perfectly retains heat, but also does not cause negative health effects. Natural materials actively occupy leading positions and displace synthetic materials [1-3]. Hemp fiber insulation material is one of the innovative material for insulation purposes. Hemp-based heat-insulating materials have a number of distinctive properties, including environmental friendliness and harmlessness. However, hemp fiber has an increased fire hazard and moisture absorption.

A significant disadvantage of insulating materials is their flammability. Flame retardant coatings have emerged as promising treatment options for improving the fire resistance of materials due to their effective, economic and economic advantages, low toxicity and low smoke generation during combustion.

To improve the fire resistance of thermal insulation materials based on renewable resources, flame re-

tardants of various compositions are used. A composition has been developed to impart fire-retardant properties to insulating materials from hemp [4].

Another requirement for building insulation is the ability of the material to maintain its properties throughout the entire life cycle. Often, materials and structures based on them are used in changing environmental conditions with variable temperature, humidity and etc. It is necessary to ensure the constancy of their properties.

Water absorption of fibrous materials leads to an increase in the coefficient of thermal conductivity, which reduces the effectiveness of thermal insulation and reduces the service life of the product. Excessive water absorption is a negative factor and must be reduced to ensure the normal functioning of the material.

The aim of this article is to study the properties of hemp insulation materials. For the test, representative samples of hemp insulation material were selected, pre-treated with the developed fire-retardant composition.

Table 1 shows the composition of the applied composition.

Table 1

Component composition of the flame retardant composition

Component name	Component Quantity
Sodium silicate	30 ml
Sodium hydrogen phosphate	30 g
Thiourea	10 g

The results obtained by scanning electron microscopy clearly demonstrate the change in the sample surface morphology caused by the condensation of silanol groups with the formation of a polymer layer. In this case, the diameter of the fibers varies from 19.65 to

50.29 micrometers. In addition, the surface of the hemp fiber after modification acquires microroughness, and SEM images show plates of particles of various shapes (Fig. 1).

Figure 1 – SEM micrographs of the surface of hemp fibers after treatment with a flame retardant composition of various resolutions

According to the results of energy-dispersive microanalysis (Fig. 2), after surface modification of the treated sample of hemp insulation material Si-2.06%, P - 3.5%, S-3.3% unevenly distributed particles are formed

Figure 2 – EDS spectrum of modified hemp fibers after treatment with flame retardant composition

Water absorption was studied according to GOST 17177.4-94 [5]. In accordance with the method of water absorption at full dipping, a comparison of the water absorption values for the treated and untreated samples with a flame retardant composition was made. It was found that the water absorption of the untreated sample is almost 3.5 times higher than that of the treated one.

Thus, it can be concluded that the fire retardant composition developed to ensure the fire resistance of hemp insulation material contributes to the formation of a thin polymer layer on the fiber with silicon, phosphorus and sulfur particles. Based on the experimental data, it can be concluded that the treatment of hemp insulation material with a fire retardant composition simultaneously reduces the material's ability to water absorption, which is critical for ensuring optimally effective thermal insulation ability and maintaining the original physical and mechanical properties of the fiber.

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